

GRAPHIC DESIGN IN THE CONTEMPORARY WORLD: NEED FOR TECHNOLOGY-DRIVEN EDUCATION IN PAKISTAN TO BRIDGE INDUSTRY AND ACADEMIA

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Abstract

In the modern age of the internet and social media, communication has become the foundation of human interaction, making the role of graphic design indispensable. This study explores the connection between communication, psychology, and visual perception within the practice of graphic design. It investigates how designers translate ideas into visual language while maintaining awareness of cultural, social, and psychological contexts. The research emphasizes that effective visual communication depends on the designer's ability to understand how audiences interpret meaning, influenced by their environment and emotions. Drawing on the perspectives of scholars such as Quentin Newark, Amy E. Arntson, Ryan Hembree, Marty Neumeier, and Salima Hashmi, this study defines graphic design as both a problem-solving process and a creative art form. It argues that while art is primarily expressive, graphic design functions as purposeful communication a balance between creativity and structure. The findings suggest that successful design is not only aesthetically appealing but also conceptually strong, evoking emotion, cognition, and identification in its viewers. Ultimately, the research positions graphic design as a bridge between visual art and communication science, shaping how societies perceive and connect through imagery in the digital age.

Introduction

With the advent of the internet and social media, the world today is the arena of communication, be it visually or otherwise hence, the role of graphic design is inevitable. The professional industry of graphic design requires designers to be able to understand the aesthetics of graphic design while keeping the industry in mind. A graphic designer must have the consciousness of cultural, social-political, and religious aspects of customers

before designing anything. It is essential to understand the psychology of the customer and any of his related historic background. To visually communicate any message to the audience, it is essential to understand what the observer is deriving out of it given their cultural and psychological context. According to Quentin Newark, graphic design is the collection of all the arts.¹ Graphic designing is how one gives meaning to the visuals around

¹ Newark, Quentin. "What is graphic design?" (2002).

him. Today, we cannot escape graphic designs especially in our urban culture. Amy E, Arntson defined graphic designing as “the design of things people sees and read.”² According to Arntson, when a graphic designer tries to create a visual imagery, he communicates with the aesthetics of the observer through his design.

In the processes of communication, everyone needs a certain medium, be it words or gestures or even a surface or an object. What makes an artist distinct from the rest is the power to change mundane objects or surfaces into aesthetic pieces which translate into emotions or feelings. Arntson considered graphic design as problem solving, and she clarified that “problems in graphic design almost always relate to visual communication, and there are specific methods of creating a design that communicates visually and conceptually.”³ From Arntson’s point of view, it could be presumed that graphic design solves problems visually. As problem solving is to make complicated issues simpler, Hembree stated, “graphic design serves as a method for improving society through effective communication that makes complicated things easier to understand and use” hence graphic designing is problem solving through communication.⁴ This communication can be

visual as well as cognitive. Many people distinguish graphic design from arts simply because art is creative, whereas graphic designing is more problem solving and problem solving is a branch of creativity hence, graphic designers can be called artists as well.⁵

Graphic design is finding a creative source to communicate, which itself is an art. However, Hembree argues how graphic designing cannot be categorized as art since the purpose of both is different. Although both processes are creative, graphic designers must use their tools to effectively communicate and, hence systematically follow required steps. Since graphic designers are seen as graphic intellectuals and critical thinkers, they deliver a concert using different mediums such as papers, concrete surfaces, ink, and colors in order to convey their idea to their customers, they are mostly called message makers as well.

Marty Neumeier asserted that the process of visual communication is like a monologue. The components to a graphic message and a monologue are the same i.e., a sender, a message, and a receiver.⁶ The graphic designer involves the customer into this creative process as the receiver and interpreter of the message. The delivered message must remain with the receiver for long as it touches their aesthetics and beyond. According to Salima Hashmi, the designer must connect with the customer on

² Arntson, Amy E. *Graphic design basics*. Cengage Learning, 2011.

³ Arntson, 3.

⁴Hembree, Ryan. *The complete graphic designer: a guide to understanding graphics and visual communication*. Rockport publishers, 2006.

⁵ Barnard, Malcolm. *Graphic design as communication*. Routledge, 2013.

⁶ Neumeier, Marty. "The Brand Gap-How to Bridge the Distance Between Business Strategy and Design. New Riders." (2006).

the level of perception, emotion, cognition, sensation, sound, and identification.⁷

Technology and Education

In modern times, technology is indispensable to education. Contemporary learning is systems involving technological adherence to maximum level. Education sector has transformed completely. From traditional pedagogical approaches to recent digital shifts causing major changes in policy making. According to Antonio Bowen, technology has effectively improved teaching and learning by optimizing classrooms and digitizing courses. Technology ensures meaningful interactions of students with their teachers and increases their learning capacity by ensuring digital resources are available, seamlessly. The power that technology has endowed to the educators is undoubtedly preeminent. Technology not only helps in the teaching and learning process but also plays an eminent role in curriculum development. Although there is no doubt in the importance that technology holds in the field of education, it has become increasingly challenging to ensure a successful transition from traditional school systems to digital systems. The curriculum development being a constructive step in advancement in education is merely the first step towards educational development in graphic design. Real challenge

lies in ensuring effective implementation of the developed curriculum.

As students of millennial generation, we are accustomed to technology and digital adaptation is not a challenge for them. Bowen highlighted importance of human capacity in the education system which not only attributes to the change in teaching and learning methodology but also efficient ways of implementing those changes. He has advocated the use of virtual learning beneficial for both students as well as teachers.⁸

Bowen suggests to the teachers and faculty members to ensure maximum inclusion of students in the teaching and learning process by enabling them in technological endeavors. One such suggestion is the use of e-portfolios. He has highlighted importance of e-portfolios in ensuring uninterrupted and resourceful learning with technological development. Scholars also highlight the importance of technology in the learning process by stating that technology has helped teachers perform their duties in a more effective and efficient manner. The teaching capability of instructors has accelerated multiple times with the use of technology. He added that technology is not mainly about computers, cell phones or iPods but it is sophisticated and seamless way of

⁷ Salima Hashmi is Art Critic, Art and Design Educationist, Former Principal National College of Arts, Lahore (She worked extensively on the art and design teaching pedagogy in Pakistan); Graphic designer IV, November 5, 2018.

⁸ Bowen, José Antonio. *Teaching naked: How moving technology out of your college classroom will improve student learning*. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.

letting students and teachers interact in a more meaningful way without any interruptions.⁹ Technology is being increasingly used by teachers across the world, there are several benefits attached to it. One of the main reasons is that it gives the teacher access to a wide array of digital tools. Students can enjoy audio-visual resources which gives an edge to the process of teaching and learning. Technology is also very useful in meeting requirements of different students who might find it difficult to learn in a traditional learning environment. The third advantage according to Sharon Smaldino is that technology optimizes a well-designed curriculum meant to meet needs of diversity of students. A modern-day curriculum cannot be implemented without audio-visual aids; hence technology remains the centre of curriculum development. Smaldino asserted that to cater different learning styles of students, learning methodologies need to be planned aptly while ensuring that instruction is meaningful as well as resourceful for the students. This education planning, if deliberated properly merging diverse learning methods, could produce the vital outcome of effective teaching and learning.

Technology is a significant tool to encourage students towards independent learning. As per Ruth Geer and Trudy-Ann Sweeney, the fundamental reason for incorporating technology into learning is to ensure

⁹Simonson, Michael, Susan M. Zvacek, and Sharon Smaldino. "Teaching and learning at a distance: Foundations of distance education 7th edition." (2019)

independent learning in students where they are provided with the resources and tools to learn at their own pace. They further added that "information and communication technologies (ICT) are essential tools in today's world; the use of ICT provides opportunity for students to learn in multiple ways and in multiple spaces."¹⁰ In their study, Geer and Sweeney conclusively admitted that technology has not only enabled students but teachers too. Geer and Sweeney further deducted that student, when given the opportunity to interact with technology, feel more empowered and well-equipped which eventually also helps the instructor achieve the learning objectives. Another study by James Fu concluded that the use of ICT in education helps students achieve quality education through effective teaching and learning.¹¹ As technology allows and encourages students to work more collaboratively, it helped them in developing collaborative skills which helped in their professional lives. Fu further added that technology encourages students to be more open and take risks which is fundamental to any learning in their lives as well. He identified that technology provides a meaningful communication to students, teachers, and administration which helps in the efficient

¹⁰ Geer, R and Trudy-Ann Sweeney. "Students' Voices about Learning with Technology," *Journal of Social Sciences* 8, no. 2 (March 26, 2012): 294-303, <https://doi.org/10.3844/jssp.2012.294.303>.

¹¹ Fu, Jo. Complexity of ICT in education: A critical literature review and its implications," *International journal of education and Development using ICT* 9, no. 1 (2013): 112-125.

learning of objectives.¹² There are several advantages of adapting digital learning tools. Students not only become tech-savvy but also become independent learners during the process of ICT incorporation. There are prominent results of correlation between ICT equipped teaching and learning and effective implementation of lesson planning. Both these positively affect students' achievement.¹³ It is deduced that the best way to ensure wholesome classroom experience where lesson objectives are fulfilled aptly is when information and communication technology is aligned with lesson objectives. Technological integration with education has a positive impact on education, however there are certain challenges attached to it which pose as obstacles to the implementers. One of the major obstacles is the transition between traditional and ICT enabled curriculum. This transition requires extensive staff training with infrastructural changes and resource availability which may be a challenge to financially deprived institutions.¹⁴

According to Inas Alkholy, incorporation of multimedia in graphic design curriculum ensures elevated experience of learning to the student and also gives the teacher freedom of exploring diverse media. He further highlights

that most teachers in the design field face serious limitations related to access to technology in the Middle East.¹⁵ The subject requires PowerPoint presentations whereas the teachers do not have access to multimedia. The pictorial resources that can be used through incorporating audio-visual prompts is not possible in traditional methods.

During various discussions with professionals of the field in Lahore, at least four main obstacles were identified. Firstly, students who try to make their ends meet find it extremely difficult to manage between studies and freelance designing.¹⁶ Secondly, when designer graduates encounter market professionals who do not have an academic background but are paid as much as them due to their technical skills, demotivates them.¹⁷ They find a prominent gap between new software in the market and the ones that they came across in their academic learning. Availability of outdated softwares in universities, also creates difficulty for students while competing with local and international markets. Thirdly, difficulty lies in the contrast between moral and ethical values they are given in their school versus what they experience in the

¹³ Cox, Margaret, Mary Webb, Chris Abbott, B. Blakely, Tony Beauchamp, and Valerie Rhodes. "ICT and pedagogy: a review of the research literature: a report to the DfES (ISBN: 1844781356)." (2004).

¹⁴ Emre, DiNC. "Prospective teachers' perceptions of barriers to technology integration in education." *Contemporary Educational Technology* 10, no. 4 (2019): 381-398.

¹⁵ Alkholy, Inas. "Using hypermedia in teaching art & design: Baroque Dutch paintings." *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)* 5, no. 3 (2010): 37-41

¹⁶ Jafri, M. Hassan. Former head of design faculty, National College of Arts. Audio, 2018.

¹⁷ Hussain, Tazeen. Head of communication design department, Indus Valley School of Design. Audio, 2020.

marketplace.¹⁸ In universities, students are given conceptual understanding of ethics however in the practical market they need to design products which do not comply with ethical constructs and where services are faked on many levels. Another major issue that creative designing capabilities of designers with degrees are usually out casted by technicians who know the software and are ready to work but for significantly higher rates and wages.¹⁹ Market stakeholders are of the view that modern curriculum development in the graphic design industry should be aligned with the need for professionalism and accuracy by the end-consumer, requirements of the professional marketplace and that of higher education standards.²⁰ Market stakeholders have highlighted the need of building multiple skills in graphic design students including aesthetic faculties, work professionalism, language proficiency, cognitive abilities, and understanding.²¹ Graphic designers should have these four capabilities: Professional design skills, academic degrees, practical experience, and creative design skills. Without these skills, it would be difficult to survive in

¹⁸ Falk, Armin, and Nora Szech. "Institutions and morals: A reply." *European Journal of Political Economy* 40 (2015): 391-394.

¹⁹ Leonard, Dorothy, and Jeffrey F. Rayport. "Spark innovation through empathic design." *Harvard business review* 75 (1997): 102-115.

²⁰ Ferguson, Brooks. *Art, commerce, and values: The relationship between creativity and integrity in the feature film development process*. Pepperdine University, 2004.

²¹ Meyer, Michael W., and Don Norman. "Changing design education for the 21st century." *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation* 6, no. 1 (2020): 13-49.

the ever-changing arena of design and technology in the modern world.²²

Psychological Perspective of Creativity in Graphic Design Education

Creativity is a major component of a human's psychological health. Since creativity is an absolute necessity in graphic design curriculum, it is essential to investigate its psychological and cultural intricacies. Creativity is mostly a by-product of culture. Since an individual's experiences are mostly formed by culture, creativity in turn is formed by cultural impact on an individual. When a person's values and life experiences are connected with his 34surrounding through interaction, it creates creativity. Culture and tradition give birth to folklore which become part of a child's imagination since childhood. This later adds with life experiences and hence forms creativity. In order to nurture problem-solving skills in students, creativity is very important. Most of the university teachers are of the view that creativity and problem solving are fundamentals of graphic designing.²³

Since creativity is crucial for diverse solutions and once a student is enrolled in graphic designing courses, he expects his teacher to teach creativity. However, creativity, according to psychologists, cannot be taught rather nurtured, enabled, and reinforced through effective teaching and learning approaches. To

²² Cheung, Pun Sin Benson. "The Making of competent graphic designers in Hong Kong: The transitional period from academia to professional practice." (2015).

²³ Alhajri, Salman Amur. "The Importance of Creativity in Teaching Graphic Design in Arab World." *Design Principles & Practice: An International Journal* 4, no. 1 (2010).

understand the role of creativity in graphic design education, it is essential to first evaluate what drives a designer towards creativity.

Graphic design is often seen as a simple process of manipulating pictures and texts. However, its basic goal is to inculcate aesthetics in a student's language where they learn the order and meaningful solutions for each message created.²⁴ The goal of education is to enrich students through creative thinking abilities. It is a complex process to deliver a meaningful message through lines, patterns, colors, texts, shapes, audios, videos, and much more. Since there are multiple options in graphic design, it is important to equip students with correct methods to explore which medium to use, when, and how. This requires creativity and problem-solving skills to cater specific needs. Idea generation process also requires mental capabilities and problem-solving skills to communicate to different audiences. Understanding interconnectedness of ideas and their practicality in the real world is also a significant skill which needs to be part of graphic design education. This competence is broadly covered under the head of creativity in the discipline of psychology.²⁵

²⁴ Alhajri, Salman Amur. "Investigating Creativity in Graphic Design Education from Psychological Perspectives," *Journal of Arts and Humanities* 06 (January 29, 2017): 69-89, <https://doi.org/10.18533/journal.v6i01.1079>.

²⁴ Kansrirat, Thawatchai and Paiboon Kiattikomol. "Essential skills of training ideas generation in graphic design for non-graphic designers in Thailand" *Global Journal of Engineering Education* 18, no. 2 (2016): 129-35.

In four years, undergraduate program Pakistani students are taught packaging, advertising, publication, and visual communications. All of these require effective skills of international standards. Since all signs, displays, and posters require an effective message with correct selection of colors, text, and technique, a graphic designer is expected to have an aesthetical as well as market-oriented eye.

According to Jesenka Pibernik, "graphic designers are delegated with the responsibility for the context and content of design messages."²⁶ Since a designer is responsible for the perceptions of the message in the minds of the audience, it is essential to have excellent cognitive skills. Graphic designers are expected to be creative and at the same time competitive in their approaches towards design. Since creativity is seen as a function of culture, the definitions for creativity change with cultural shifts. Different cultures perceive creativity with varied approaches, therefore creative minds are those who are seen as problem solvers in the context of their surroundings. Thus, the role of creativity remains fundamental in graphic design education.

Studies suggest that "there exists a continuous need to explore the cross cultural and indigenous elements of creativity."²⁷ This aids

²⁶ Pibernik, Jesenka, Diana Milcic, and Josip Bota. "Pressure toward Creativity: Individual/Group Work in Student Design Competition," in *DS 66-2: Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Design Creativity (ICDC 2010)*, 2010.

²⁷ Alhajri, Salman Amur. "Investigating creativity in graphic design education from psychological

in observing the effect culture have on creativity and its link with students' psychology as well. Such findings are very meaningful for curriculum developers who work to build a skill set for design students. Graphic design education aims to develop creativity in students through appropriate curriculum design and effective teaching methodologies. These definitions are Western models of creativity which promote problem solving and inventiveness as major features of creativity. Graphic design education primarily helps to solve problems at hand and while this is seen as a fundamental aspect of creativity, this is not the only factor contributing to it. James Barnard emphasized that "creativity could be appropriately thought of as a mere cultural production and advancements in the field of graphic design are examples of cultural production."²⁸

Curriculum developers mainly focus on the core skills required for the specific subject. For graphic designing, it is problem-solving and creativity which leads to best communication of the message. Curriculum development in graphic designing must be targeted towards excellent cognitive skills to ensure manifestation of creativity in the projects. Subject-specific teaching and learning methodologies should be introduced in curriculum to cater particular learning objectives and effective classroom interactions.

perspectives." *Journal of Arts and Humanities* 6, no. 01 (2017): 69-85.

²⁸ Barnard, Malcolm. *Graphic design as communication*. Routledge, 2013.

The curriculum for graphic designing should include group activities in order to foster collaborative skills with effective communication. When learners perform problem solving activities in groups, it simulates studio experiences where a team works towards solving a particular objective. It is recommended that open-ended problem-solving challenges along with group tasks are assigned to graphic design students, so they learn to communicate while collaborating with their peers. This will also encourage peer-learning. When learners' cognitive skills are well groomed, they become enabled to easily adapt to any changes required to deal with professional life situations. In North America, workshops have become part of graphic design education.²⁹ These workshops not only help students actualize their special potentials while increasing their contemporary knowledge set pertinent to graphic design education. These workshops help students build their cognitive skills to the level that they become able to understand the core skills related to graphic design and how these skills are relevant in the marketplace.

Graphic Design education in Pakistan started as a craft to contribute industrial requirements, assumed an academic identity and then became a market oriented research and practice. It is intriguing that the changing relationship of Graphic Design education and

²⁹ Park*, Chris. "The graduate teaching assistant (GTA): Lessons from North American experience." *Teaching in Higher Education* 9, no. 3 (2004): 349-361.

its corresponding industry has not been documented.

The absorption of graphic designers in the communication industry of Pakistan and the hundreds of students graduating in the discipline create this illusion that the process is much tangible and result oriented. Even a cursory observation reveals that this surge is due to the economic forces and not due to creative and aesthetically inspiring potential of the discipline. There is a need to examine graphic design education and its impact on industry in the local setting to move on to third stage, where we could intelligently intervene in the domain of graphic design education and thereby improve the face of communication industry.

The education sector of Pakistan is developing significantly with advent of the internet. Contemporary approaches towards education are primarily being adapted by the respective sector. In many regions of Pakistan, the national language is prevalent in communication and on primary level syllabus is taught in Urdu language, albeit the private sector mostly offers English as the medium of communication and education. The variant fee structure in Pakistan creates a clear class difference between public and private students. This difference in quality of education makes it difficult to ensure that education of art and design is ubiquitously accessible for all learners. Most of the education available on art and design is in English medium and the latest mode of education related to graphic design

requires provisions of computers and latest soft wares along with other creative technology mediums. Most of the students do not have access to such facilities in Pakistan.

Industry and Academia

Pakistani educationists have been identifying this need of bridging the gap between private and public education and are focused on making certain changes within the curriculum. It intends to make art as a compulsory part of the curriculum in both public and private education institutes, as in public education institutes there is no art or art related course within the curriculum. The educationists have also highlighted the unavailability of basic modern tools, techniques, and soft wares within the higher education institutes offering art and design education. According to educationists the unavailability of latest essential technology for design education is creating hindrance for student's learning. There is also an unavailability of trained staff/teachers within the public and private educational institutes due to which students are not able to get the required level of skills demanded by the related industry. Many art educationists are taking personal initiatives to ensure that art and design students become highly skilled professionals across the country which is only possible when institutes in Pakistan have access to all the necessary resources. They must have highly skilled teachers and work force with the best possible advance art and design curriculum to ensure that students get an advance level of education.

Pakistani universities have seen different evolutionary stages in the last few decades. Art has been a major part of Pakistani culture and was informally part of education and industry till 1950s. It was after 1960s that art education became a formal part of the education system within the universities. Art took form of academia in the later phase of its evolution in Pakistan; nevertheless it was part of traditional craft in Pakistan.

The developments achieved by graphic design industry in Pakistan and professional/academicians contributions have made it today an important industry. During the past and then in the present it was analyzed and discussed, also importance of Graphic Design teaching pedagogy and challenges that are faced by this industry require to be analyzed.

The perception related to the graphic design education among the Pakistani academics is considered that has not been discussed before in Pakistan, similar to a study by Alan F. Cliff and Rob Woodward in 2004, the studies on the topic related to perception of academics about the knowledge in design schools "How do academics come to know and the structure and contestation of discipline-specific knowledge in a Design school."

Modern design education needs to be at least aligned with technical knowledge, according to requirements set up internationally. Hence, the dire need of an updated curriculum aligned with international industry is inevitable. The primary industry making major

influence on art and design education in Pakistan is graphic, textile and fashion industry. Learners need to be trained in a way that they can compete with international standards of quality in design. Art and design education has always been integral to national individuality, traditional ideals, and global identity of Pakistan. In Pakistan, graphic design is still under deployment and disagreement as far as the educational policies are concerned.

Art and design curriculum being taught within the Pakistani universities absences advance level quality content, thus not catering much involvement of technology and modern design methods, moreover the teaching faculty in universities needs to be more consummate, faculty trainings are much needed to meet the new teaching paradigm challenges in the field of Art and Design so as to connect students skills and concepts with industrial demands, which is the major hindrance to get aligned with the professional world.

Design being the main industry in Pakistan, is looking for graduates who can compete on an international level. The design industry now has global marketplace to cater. Demand and supply play a pivotal role in an industry. The demands set by consumers are the driving force for any designer within the design industry. With globalization and the advent of social media, manufacturers now have to move towards a more professional approach hence pushing the Academia to produce workforce that is well-trained and well-versed with modern approaches of art and design.

Manufacturers require highly trained and well-qualified designers. Be it textile, interior or graphic; all design industries now have fundamental requirement of well-qualified and practiced individuals who can compete with modern standards and challenges. The trend towards fine arts is now evolving into more industry-oriented options such as graphic design, textile design, multimedia arts, architecture, or interior design, game design. In Pakistan, private universities are mainly contributing towards well qualified human resource as faculty and entrepreneurs. The maximum exposure a student gets in the name of art and design education is merely the replication of objects. The cognitive ability to create, interpret and inspire design is missing mainly from the objectives of the design curriculum. Even at the higher education level, graphic design education lacks in depth courses which can bring a difference and are needed to compete with international standards. According to academicians and professionals, Pakistani educational institutes do not have well-defined curriculum for art and design related subject.

In order to encourage learners to imagine and create on their own, there is a dire need of an advance curriculum which nourishes critical thinking of the learners and can meet the new challenges of Artificial Intelligence (AI). The prevailing curriculum which promotes rote learning in Pakistan cannot produce creative minds required to compete with AI. Moreover, the creative process is not nurtured in public

institutes whereas in some of the private institutes the curriculum is designed as per the international standards. The major problem is their fee structure which is so high that that students belonging to middle class families are not able to afford it. Some other issues within the public institutes can be resolved by the provision of highly efficient and trained teaching faculty that can implement the vision of independent learning in learners, in order to bridge the gap between academia and industry, many steps are needed to be taken, including introduction of latest scholarship on art and design, comprehensive design curriculum, qualified faculty, introduction of modern courses and pedagogy, and cost-effective education. Together these things can make an enormous difference for the learners and can provide them with better environment to develop extraordinary creative abilities to create and complete a design project and fulfil the industrial needs and develop an impact to cover up industry and academia gap.

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